
COUNCIL ON
LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

THIRTIETH
ANNUAL REPORT/1986

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1785 Massachusetts Ave., N.W.
Washington, D.C. 20036

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine* . . . Paris, 1588. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, with the following explanation: "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." The engraving has appeared in each annual report since that time.

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2. Effective July 1986.

3. Deceased, September 1985.

4. Mr. Cook, Mr. Cummings, and Mr. Wright were elected to succeed Mr. Baker, Mr. Humphry, and Mr. Vosper at the November 1985 Directors' meeting.

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5. Resigned, June 1986.

6. Resigned, December 1985.

7. Resigned, August 1985.

8. Beginning in April 1986.

9. Beginning in June 1986.

10. Beginning in January 1986.

11. Resigned, February 1986.

Fred Carrington Cole 1912–1986

Fred Carrington Cole was a professor of history, an academic administrator, and a university president. He was also the Ford Foundation advisor who stimulated the discussions that led to the formation of the Council on Library Resources in 1956. From that time until his death on May 6, 1986, Fred Cole was closely tied to CLR, first as a careful observer, then as a Board member for twenty-four years and as president for ten.

For those who knew him, there was seldom doubt about his convictions or intentions, but because he was a master at working through others, his trail is more often than not blazed only by his shadow. He provided direction and created the opportunities that made progress possible. He also measured results in simple declarative sentences.

As an historian, he knew that scholarship and libraries were inseparable; as a teacher, he knew that energetic librarians enriched both instruction and learning; as an administrator, he knew the value of responsible management; as a man who measured others by their aspirations, he knew that professional performance was governed by more than techniques. It was this wisdom and understanding that shaped CLR during his presidency and still guides it today.

Programs that developed and demonstrated the value of closer ties between library services and teaching transformed the role of collegiate libraries. Stronger connections between librarians and the academic community were established. Research libraries were recognized as the complex enterprises that they are, and their management was recast and remarkably improved through many CLR-stimulated and -funded activities. Individual librarians of promise were helped to flourish and those of proven distinction were encouraged to expand their influence. The organizational, intellectual, and national boundaries of libraries were all expanded during Fred Cole's years as CLR's president. His personal horizons became ours.

Fred Cole was respected greatly by those who worked with him. He combined a firm sense of direction with a fine sense of humor. He—and his graceful leadership—will be missed by past and present staff. His colleagues on the Board of Directors are grateful to him for serving their common cause so well.

PROGRAM REVIEW

Introduction

This report marks CLR's thirtieth year and, like those published at the end of our first and second decades, it reviews activity over the previous ten years and provides a full record for the twelve months ending June 30, 1986. There has been no slackening of the pace from one decade to the next. The record also reminds us of the consistency of purpose of research libraries and the Council alike. This should be no surprise, given the fact that continuity of effort is inherent in the library obligation to merge the current with the cumulative record.

But stability in purpose does not imply tranquility. The past ten years—and, even more, the past thirty years—provide strong evidence that the reputation of libraries as unchanging, conservative institutions has outlived the facts. In the years since 1956, libraries, especially academic and research libraries, have undergone a revolution in how they do their work. A strong case could be made that leading libraries have changed and improved more than any other of society's educational and cultural enterprises.

Library facilities on university and college campuses have been largely rebuilt; many, in fact, now need renovation, reflecting intensity of use. On many campuses, half or more of the population use the library every day. Responding to much-expanded research activity, collections have increased in scope and size, not simply because of the accumulation of routine acquisitions but because global coverage of an increasing volume of publishing has become the norm. In many general research libraries, only half of annual acquisitions are in the English language. Staff size has grown and staff composition has changed, a direct result of expanded collecting activity and enrollment. In turn, substantial budget increases, closely tied to rising university educational expenditures, have required the use of sophisticated management methods, even as size, costs, and the nature of the times have combined to stimulate development of complex organizational structures.

But growth alone, no matter how remarkable, does not fully describe the transformation of research libraries in the three decades that correspond to the Council's own history. Computer and complementary technologies for telecommunications and data storage have reshaped library operations and have

redefined service prospects. Less visible than technology and less advanced, but perhaps in the long run no less influential, is a shift from insularity to interdependence. Research libraries (less so their users) are irreversibly committed to collaboration simply because, given the magnitude of their task, there is no other reasonable course. Technology supports collaboration, and, in at least some ways, the broadened base of collaboration will provide the setting that will fulfill the promise of technology.

The research library of today is obviously a different enterprise than it was thirty years ago, and in this, a CLR anniversary year, it is proper to note that the Council on Library Resources has been an important, and we think useful, party to the process of change. By concentrating on “generic” matters rather than on the needs of single institutions, we have played both lead and supporting roles. In every area—buildings, collections, library organization and management, librarianship, financial control, the application of technology, and the development of effective collaborative operations—CLR has sought to be useful to libraries and those who depend on them. We have worked to strengthen communication among library leaders, nationally and internationally, and between libraries and the scholarly groups they serve and the university officers who, in the end, need to concur with policy decisions and provide required support.

It is probable that the innovations of the past thirty years have set the course for the future, but the hard part still lies ahead—refining what is in place and concentrating on performance rather than invention. This is not to say that innovation is at an end, but one of the hazards of an era of dynamic technology is the failure to distinguish between what is different and what is better. The task for libraries is to do better what they have always been charged with doing; that is, to collect, preserve, organize, and provide equitable access to the human record. The technical and organizational innovations of past years are the new means. In a sense, the present *is* the future that has been proclaimed, and it is learning to live in this new present that will dominate the work of librarians and call for the constructive participation of library users in the decade to come. Technology must be made to perform and to live up to its promise.

We will all have to learn to cope with complexity—revision of definitions of intellectual property, library financing, technology-based operations and services, shifts in organization and governance, dispersion of resources and users alike, information commercialization, and shifting lines of demarcation for disciplines and research activity are only some of the factors that are affecting libraries. At heart, the perception and definition of what a research library is and how it works must change—it must change in the minds not only of librarians but of faculty and university officers as well. In this new setting, libraries must be consciously and dramatically reshaped if they are to accomplish their long-established and still absolutely essential mission. The nature of the change cannot be left to chance.

What can CLR do to help? In part, we will try to do what we are asked to do. But we will also try to pull, as well as be pushed. As this report suggests, our program is tailored to the times. We are convinced that too little is known about the ways that the information pertinent to scholarship and research is generated, made accessible, and used. The research component of our program is designed to stimulate purposeful investigation into such matters and to consider the implications of findings for the organization of libraries and universities.

Second, collaborative ventures to support operations and expand service capabilities remain an important area for attention. The key issues center on comprehensive coverage of recorded information in all formats, preservation, bibliographic systems, and the management process itself. Success in each area is essential if the cause of equitable access to information is to be advanced.

Finally, and possibly most important, the profession of librarianship needs careful attention. We believe that, just as libraries are being redefined, the perception and the reality of the profession itself must change. Society's prospects in this information age will be governed not only by technology or systems or money, but by the performance of the leaders who are charged with wisely using the new capabilities to accomplish old goals. Better ways must be found to recruit exceptional people to our profession, to provide them with the understanding and skills that are required, and to make full use of their talents.

Stimulating productive research, encouraging constructive collaborative action, and enlisting and assisting the right help seem a modest enough assignment for CLR, but if the past is an indication, there is probably more to it than meets the eye.

Warren J. Haas

The Council's Third Decade

Any review of CLR activity, whether for one year or ten, should begin by recognizing that without financial support from many foundations, there would be nothing to report. The Ford Foundation founded CLR and funded it for two decades. Perhaps the most remarkable feature of this past decade is the fact that eleven other private foundations, along with the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) and several other government agencies, have chosen to join Ford and to support the work not only of CLR but of many academic and research libraries across the country. There is no stronger indicator of the importance of libraries to scholarship and teaching. The foundations that provide funds are also a source of guidance and advice, and libraries owe these foundations a great deal. They also have a continuing obligation to use the funds provided in a way that will promote long-term improvement in performance and service.

In addition to NEH, the organizations that have funded CLR during the past decade are:

The Carnegie Corporation of New York
The Commonwealth Fund
The Exxon Education Foundation
The Ford Foundation
The J. Paul Getty Trust
The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation
The Lilly Endowment, Inc.
The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation
National Commission on Libraries and Information Science
National Library of Medicine
National Science Foundation
The Pew Memorial Trust
The Rockefeller Foundation
The Alfred P. Sloan Foundation
The H.W. Wilson Foundation

While the topics for attention by CLR have not changed dramatically during the past ten years, their complexity has increased. Council activities and funds have supported libraries, universities, related organizations, and individuals. Our efforts, as has been the case for thirty years, have been aimed at improving library performance and services for the benefit of users.

Bibliographic Services

During its second decade, the Council supported the development of computer-based bibliographic systems by a few key libraries. By 1976, it was clear that virtually all research libraries would have to find ways to automate their internal operations to improve operating efficiency and to link their resources and services to those of other libraries across the country. Large sums were invested in bibliographic automation by the nation's universities as, increasingly, administrators realized the need to support scholarship by improving access to information about information.

The Council's *Twenty-first Annual Report* noted that the solution to reducing unit costs of operating libraries lay in the development of a national library and information system that would facilitate the sharing of resources and eliminate wasteful duplication of effort. Further, it stated that "the first step in creating a national library and information system must be the development of a comprehensive, economical, cooperative method of preparing acceptable bibliographic records and making them readily available, on a machine-readable or manual basis, to all libraries: a system of national bibliographic control."

In retrospect, the concept of a tightly structured national bibliographic system was naive. The heterogeneity that is manifest in other aspects of education was shown to be dominant in bibliographic matters as well, yet the motivation for such a system ultimately proved valid in the evolution of plans for a logical nationwide bibliographic system.

Early in the decade, a National Periodicals Center was envisioned as an important step toward resource sharing, with the primary goal of improving access to periodical literature for libraries and, thus, for their users. At the request of the Library of Congress, CLR staff prepared a technical development plan for a United States national periodicals center, to which all libraries, networks, and consortia would have access. The plan was designed to increase the availability of periodical literature while protecting the rights of authors and publishers. Much work and initial enthusiasm did not prove to be sufficient, however. Ultimately, the concerns of publishers and the inability of the library community to speak with one voice kept the National Periodicals Center from becoming a reality.

With this evidence that a national operating agency would not be accepted, ways to provide cost-effective library services and products had to be reconsidered. The importance of bibliographic coordination remained unquestioned, and in response a proposal to establish a Bibliographic Service

Development Program was shaped by leading library organizations; funding totalling \$5.8 million was provided to CLR by seven private foundations and the National Endowment for the Humanities. CLR named a Program Committee to guide the complicated task of designing a logical nationwide bibliographic system. By 1980, the need to disperse responsibility was acknowledged: "It has been thought for some time that a national bibliographic data base physically located in a single place is unlikely to evolve. A de facto substitute seems more likely if the major existing bibliographic data bases, taken in the aggregate, can be considered as the 'national' data base."

With this understanding, the Bibliographic Service Development Program was the focus of much of the Council's time, energy, and funds from its inception in 1978 until mid-1986. Work of many individuals and organizations was funded through BSDP.

In 1975, CLR funds were provided for the second edition of the *Anglo-American Cataloguing Rules*. Designed to improve uniformity of bibliographic records for computerized databases, the new code is not without its critics. Most librarians agree, however, that international bibliographic control is improved and, because the code has been generally accepted by U.S. libraries, it has influenced cataloging and catalog use.

CLR's funding and management of the Conversion of Serials (CONSER) project drew to a close in 1978, but interest and support for specific projects continued. A grant was made to the National Library of Canada to publish CONSER records on computer-output microfiche. The National Library of Canada provides a copy of the microfiche to LC for U.S. distribution. More recently, a grant was awarded to the Association of Research Libraries for management of the CONSER Abstracting and Indexing Project. This joint effort between ARL and the National Federation of Abstracting and Indexing Services adds to the utility of the CONSER database by providing information on serial coverage by many abstracting and indexing services.

Many network-related projects have been sponsored through grants to such organizations as OCLC Online Computer Library Center, NELINET (New England Library Network), and MINITEX (Minnesota Interlibrary Telecommunications Exchange). One of the farthest-reaching efforts in this area stemmed from a past grant to Stanford University to improve the efficiency of BALLOTS, making it possible to support a large network of users. In 1978, the Research Libraries Group (RLG) announced that it would use BALLOTS for its network system. The two principal nationwide databases, OCLC and RLG, have helped hundreds of libraries, especially in cataloging, interlibrary loan, and other operational tasks, by making it possible for libraries to pool information about their resources. These bibliographic-based services now also support cooperative projects in preservation and collection development.

Essential to the success of a decentralized "national" system is the Linked Systems Project (LSP), established in 1980 as the Linked Authority Systems Project. The Research Libraries Group, the Washington Library Network

(now Western Library Network), and the Library of Congress joined forces to establish the technical capacity to support a nationwide shared authority file system. The three organizations, ultimately joined by OCLC, undertook construction of a Standard Network Interconnection to link computer systems. Construction of the Standard Network Interconnection, a complicated task, absorbed much BSDP effort over five years and resulted in a landmark achievement: the set of telecommunication protocols being tested and installed at the end of the period. The first application of the link, transferring authority records, is in the early stages of operation, and work is under way on a second application, the transfer of bibliographic records. The LSP protocols are based on the International Standards Organization/Open Systems Interconnection model to help assure that linking can extend beyond United States borders.

With the assurance of full participation in LSP by the major utilities and the adoption of LSP protocols by increasing numbers of commercial vendors, CLR's role is greatly reduced. Once it is fully operational, the link will allow for the comprehensive nationwide bibliographic base that will enable users, no matter where they are, to determine the existence and location of bibliographic items. To monitor progress, to establish management policies as needed, to set development priorities, and to assure conformance, two on-going committees have been established: the LSP Technical Committee and the LSP Policy Committee.

As national bibliographic databases grew, local applications kept pace through the implementation of online systems. A number of CLR-sponsored meetings, studies, and publications were related to design, development, management, and training for online catalogs. The great strength of BSDP has been the involvement of many librarians, all working toward the same end.

Several projects to strengthen the quality and range of databases were also funded. The ARL Microforms Project was established in 1981 to improve bibliographic access to microfilm collections in American and Canadian libraries by adding records for items included in microfilm sets, but never cataloged separately. The project improves access to an important part of library collections. In a related project, ARL was funded to plan a strategy for coordinated retrospective conversion of bibliographic records, enabling individual libraries to lower the costs of converting traditional card catalogs to online catalogs.

International Activities

The International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) continued to expand with the assistance of a CLR grant of \$75,000 in 1979 for program development and an additional \$70,000 award for special projects dealing with copyright of bibliographic records, conversion of copyrighted material for the use of the handicapped, and preservation of library materials. Support since 1980 has totalled \$134,800, including a

1983 grant of \$114,000 for planning new programs, particularly preservation, work on transborder data flow, and the development of international MARC. IFLA's remarkable growth and revitalization since the early 1970s, in part the result of CLR financial assistance, makes it the primary international organization concerned with library and information services.

In 1974, CLR provided funds to extend the IFLA Cataloguing Secretariat into an International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control. This Office, located at the British Library, functions as a catalyst for and coordinator of practical activities to stimulate nations to assume responsibility for preparing and making available bibliographic records of their own publications, using accepted standards to ensure that the records can readily be used in manual and machine-readable systems. A grant in 1977 extended CLR support through June 30, 1981. In 1980, the Office published *UNIMARC: Universal MARC Format* (2nd edition revised), which was accepted by a number of national libraries as a communication format for bibliographic information. International acceptance of the format makes sharing records and resources among nations more feasible.

Library Management and Services

By the end of fiscal 1977, CLR had provided the Association of Research Libraries' Office of Management Studies with just over \$500,000. Another grant of \$326,500 was made in 1978 for a five-year Academic Library Program (1979–1984), which prepared 77 librarians to assist libraries in carrying out self-study and training programs. OMS's various programs, especially the Management Skills Institute, have added considerably to the knowledge and skills of research library staffs.

The College Library Program, funded jointly by CLR and the National Endowment for the Humanities, was active from 1969 to 1983. Designed to increase the library's role in the teaching process, the funded projects brought together librarians, administrators, faculty, and sometimes students. Bibliographic instruction workshops, supported at several institutions, promoted the idea that library and instructional functions are educationally inseparable.

Professional Education

Throughout its history, CLR has provided assistance to promising individuals in the profession of librarianship. In earlier years, the pattern was established with CLR Fellowships for individuals wishing to pursue relatively short-term research projects. Other programs made it possible for librarians to pursue advanced degrees in subject areas and for those holding Ph.D.s in subject fields to acquire the professional library science degree.

Of longest standing is the Academic Library Management Intern Program, which was begun in CLR's second decade and continued throughout the third. Many former CLR interns have been appointed to directorships and assistant or associate directorships in academic libraries.

In 1980, CLR initiated the Professional Education and Training Program for Research Librarianship (PETREL) as a way to focus more attention on the education of librarians. PETREL funds have been concentrated in three areas: recruitment of highly qualified students to library schools; creation of special academic programs for newly appointed library administrators; and a series of conferences for discussion of current issues and future library needs.

In 1981, the University of Michigan was funded to attract especially talented students from liberal arts colleges to a course of study in research librarianship. After three classes of interns, the program has now been integrated into the regular curriculum.

The UCLA Senior Fellows Program, first offered in August 1982, provides an intensive academic program for library administrators. New courses were designed by faculty from several schools within UCLA, and much of the content has since been incorporated into the regular curriculum. Three classes of Senior Fellows have completed the program; two more are scheduled.

The Frontiers conferences were designed to bring together leading library educators, library directors, and academic administrators to discuss the topics of greatest concern to libraries. The first conference was hosted by UCLA in 1981, the second by the University of British Columbia in 1983. Both resulted in important publications.

The Planning and Implementation Grant Program was designed to encourage universities to plan and carry out the curricular changes needed to meet special needs. Beginning in 1984, CLR offered planning grants of up to \$5,000 to fifteen library schools that submitted a description of proposed processes and objectives. Subsequently, three program implementation grants were awarded to the University of Wisconsin, Madison, the University of Chicago, and Louisiana State University.

The Cooperative Research Program was instituted in 1982 to provide small grants to cover incremental costs of research undertaken by teams of teaching faculty and librarians. The program's objectives are to promote more communication between library educators and practitioners, to encourage research on practical library problems, and to build research skills.

A program of Internships for Recent Graduates was started in 1985. Grants were awarded on a competitive basis to libraries that designed especially promising internship programs for newly hired staff to provide a broad university perspective and to maintain professional interests. Four grants had been awarded by mid-1986. The programs will enable librarians to function more successfully in the academic environment early in their careers, and should serve as models for the creation of similar programs elsewhere.

Preservation

Preservation has long been a programmatic interest of CLR. In the Council's first decade, the emphasis was on technical aspects of preservation, with most of the activity centering on the work of the Barrow Laboratory. More

recently, the focus has shifted dramatically to assist libraries actively involved in preservation work to develop a national strategy for preserving the nation's documentary record.

The Committee on Production Guidelines for Book Longevity was established in May 1979 with a meeting sponsored by the Council and the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation. The Committee's *Interim Report on Book Paper*, issued in April 1981, drew attention to the importance of using acid-free paper in the publication of scholarly books. In mid-1982, CLR funded work by the American National Standards Institute to develop a formal standard, *Permanence of Paper for Printed Library Materials* (American National Standards Organization Z39.48-1984), which was approved August 27, 1984. The ANSI standard is based on the work of the Committee.

In 1982, the Committee issued *Longevity in Book Binding*, in which it made recommendations concerning binding methods and the kinds of materials used. The Committee's two reports and the results of the survey to determine how widely acid-free paper was being used were published in *Book Longevity* in December 1982. The Committee's work set a precedent by specifying an acceptable level of quality for scholarly books and provided librarians with a means to judge the longevity of their collections. In mid-1986, CLR funded the National Information Standards Organization to begin developing a standard for hard cover edition bindings, as recommended by the Committee.

In June 1984 the Exxon Education Foundation made available \$1.5 million to create the Mid-Atlantic States Cooperative Preservation Service, to establish a national planning effort for preservation, and to promote wider understanding of the preservation problem.

The Committee on Preservation and Access, formed in 1984, published its report, *Brittle Books*, in April 1986. In addition to calling for a permanent Commission to guide the national preservation effort, the Committee recommended funding studies of the magnitude of the preservation problem, the costs of preservation microfilming, and the life expectancy of optical disks. The Commission, established in the spring of 1986, will encourage and assist libraries to integrate their preservation activities into a national program. An Advisory Council, including representatives from concerned organizations, has been formed to promote participation of all disciplines; to encourage support by involved and interested library, archive, and academic professional organizations; and to provide general policy guidance for the Commission itself.

During the decade, several topics were identified for special attention: access to information, economics and funding of research libraries, and information research.

Access to Information

Increasingly, as CLR programs evolved, it became evident that a dominant question concerns the role of the library in the university in this technological era.

For many years, CLR has emphasized bibliographic issues and the internal operations of libraries, in keeping with its original purpose. Progress in those areas and recent technological developments have encouraged taking a more expansive view of libraries and their services. Equitable access to information has become an overt rather than an implied objective of much of the Council's activity. With Ford Foundation funding, CLR began to promote a concept of access that includes all information of worth and excludes no individual or group. To make its position known, the CLR Board of Directors issued a statement, "Scholarship, Research, and Access to Information," which has been widely endorsed by the library community.

A contract with Information Systems Consultants Inc. produced a comprehensive review of current document delivery activities among the full spectrum of service providers. The resulting report assessed what further knowledge was needed for information delivery planning and suggested a method for collecting that knowledge.

The National Collections Inventory Project (NCIP) began in 1983. Its purpose is to develop tools and procedures needed to describe research library collections, with an eye toward making the material fully accessible to all in the scholarly community. NCIP is based on RLG's program to develop a collections conspectus and has been adopted by many research libraries.

Many small grants have been made to enable exploration of technological opportunities for enhancing access, studies of user requirements for information resources, and assessment of database quality.

Economics and Funding of Research Libraries

A two-year Seminar on the Economics of Research Libraries, funded by the Lilly Endowment, was formed to investigate questions related to library financial matters, especially in the context of new technologies and expanded cooperation among libraries. Librarians were encouraged to give more emphasis to strategic planning. The Seminar commissioned research and analytical studies, promoted discussions on a number of campuses, encouraged publication of research findings, and promoted change in the scope and quality of economic data collected and analyzed by the Association of Research Libraries.

The report of the Seminar, *The Economics of Research Libraries* by Dr. Martin Cummings, was issued in April 1986.

Research Program

The changes resulting from computers, telecommunications technologies, and text storage systems as they affect the generation, distribution, organization, and use of information prompted the development of an expanded research program. The program is meant to encourage exploration of the issues and questions raised by a changing information structure, with special attention to the needs of faculty and students and the services and responsibilities of academic and research libraries.

To accomplish these objectives, CLR intends to establish three or four university research centers, create a grant program for individual research, and undertake a set of complementary activities designed to evaluate research and promote the use of findings by library and university management.

The first university center to be funded is the University of California, Los Angeles. A grant of \$400,000 was awarded late in 1985 for "Long-Range Strategic Planning for Libraries and Information Resources in the Research University." Universitywide committees and task forces are at work at UCLA to (a) better understand the relationship between information resources and the work of scholars and teachers, especially in the context of technological change and in the recognition of differences among disciplines; and (b) determine how the university should organize so as to best meet these requirements. Work is under way on such topics as information characteristics, user requirements, and the structure of future information systems for specific disciplines.

Grant, Contract, and Project Expenses by Program Area 1977–1986

(Total: approx. \$11.6 million)

Explanation of Categories

- | | |
|---------------------------------|---|
| Bibliographic Services | Includes all grants and contracts for bibliographic activities and systems automation. |
| International Activities | Includes grants to such organizations as the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, as well as funding for international travel for study and conferences. |
| Preservation | Preservation activity was at a low level for much of the decade. |
| Professional Education | Includes all aspects of the education and professional development of librarians. Examples: the Academic Library Management Intern Program, the UCLA Senior Fellows Program, the ARL Institutes for Library Educators, and CLR Fellowships. |

- Management** Includes grants stemming from the Seminar on the Economics of Research Libraries and projects funded through the ARL Office of Management Studies.
- Research** Grants contributing to the White House Conference on Libraries and Information Services, the ACLS Office of Scholarly Communication, and CLR's recently expanded research program.
- Resources** Includes grants relating to information delivery, access, library consortia, interlibrary loan, and collaborative collection development.
- Miscellaneous** Includes specialized projects and conferences.

The Year 1985/1986

Grant and program-related expenses increased by more than 18 percent over the previous year. The Council's expanding research program and a resurgent preservation agenda accounted for much of this growth, while bibliographic activities, long the dominant CLR undertaking, showed a substantial decline, at least when measured in financial terms.

Research

A much-expanded research program took shape after a period of planning and experiment, and the first major grant was made during the year. The intent of the program, described in a widely distributed brochure, is to encourage investigation of the effect of the "information revolution" on scholarship, research, and teaching. It is anticipated that CLR will assist a few universities as they address issues raised by the increasing growth of information technologies and underscored by economic forces and organizational change. In addition, a new series of grants available to individuals undertaking research on specific topics has been established and periodic conferences to report on research activities are planned, the first of which is scheduled for early September 1986.¹

The initial university center has been established at UCLA, where most academic components of the University have joined forces for long-range strategic planning for libraries and information resources. The UCLA work, viewed by CLR as a prototype for other university efforts, is managed by Robert Hayes, Dean of the Graduate School of Library and Information Science. The project is designed to

explore the effect of technology on the ways information resources will be used in the research university;

seek better understanding of the information requirements of individual disciplines; and

1. Members of the Research Advisory Panel are listed in Appendix A.

determine the role of information resources in the work of individual scholars, researchers, students, and teachers.

The results of the research and analytical studies to be undertaken in the next two or three years will help determine how the university should plan and organize to meet established requirements. It is anticipated that the research program will benefit both UCLA and many other institutions. A strategic plan for consideration by UCLA faculty and administrators will be constructed as the basis for the development and management of information resources at the University. A second objective, directly related to the first, is explicit testing of a process for academic strategic planning for information resources. The documentation of the process and the results will be made available to other institutions. Formal research projects of sufficient magnitude and importance to represent major contributions to the advancement of knowledge in this field will be identified by the advisory committee and disciplinary task forces. The research itself will be carried out under the direction of many UCLA faculty members. Published and internal reports will provide the base for discussions with other institutions and individuals with parallel research projects.

The CLR Economics Seminar, an earlier research enterprise and a precursor to the expanded research program, culminated in the publication of *The Economics of Research Libraries*, by Martin M. Cummings. The monograph synthesizes the reports and discussions that were part of the two-year-long program that involved academic officers, economists, and library directors in an exploration of the response of universities to changing economic conditions and new demands for information resources.² The book, which also provides a comprehensive overview of recent publications pertinent to library costs and funding, has been widely distributed.

Research Program Projects, 1985/1986

University of California, Los Angeles

To develop a university-based research program focused on the issues, problems, and needs for research with respect to long-range strategic planning for libraries and information resources in the research university of the future.

Economics Seminar Projects, 1985/1986

American Library Association

To partially support a Public Library Association Cost Analysis Task Force project to develop a manual that defines cost concepts and provides methods

2. Participants in the October 1985 Seminar are listed in Appendix A.

of collecting and analyzing cost data for public libraries. *Cost Finding for Public Libraries: A Manager's Handbook* was published in 1985.

Association of Research Libraries

To collect data on the costs of automation in ARL member libraries. *The Automation Inventory of Research Libraries* was published in August 1985.

National Association of College and University Business Officers

To study strategic planning and budgeting for university libraries and the impact of technological changes on library operations.

Program Activities, 1985/1986

Seminar on the Economics of Research Libraries

October 28–30, 1985 (Wye Plantation, Maryland)

Library Operations

Traditionally, CLR has assisted the academic and research library community in its search for collaborative approaches to meet service obligations. Activities tend to fall into one of three primary areas: resources and preservation, bibliographic systems, and access.

Resources and Preservation

Preservation figured prominently in both staff effort and grant activity during the year. The central element was the work of the Committee on Preservation and Access, which completed its assignment with the publication of the report, *Brittle Books*, in April 1986.³ The Committee assessed the extent and importance of the problem of brittle books and concluded that concentrated attention over a long period of time is required if an important segment of recorded information is not to be lost.

Participants in a CLR-sponsored meeting at Wye Plantation in late March reviewed the recommendations of the Committee and encouraged continuation and expansion of the effort. As a result, a new Commission on Preservation and Access has been established and its operating costs funded for an initial period of three years by several universities and foundations (including CLR).⁴ A complementary National Advisory Council on Preservation, including representatives of organizations that have an interest in the success of preservation efforts, has been formed to help assure effective communication between the Commission itself and all who can contribute to meeting the responsibilities it has assumed.

The Commission will work on behalf of the libraries and organizations that must, in the end, do the work of preservation. Simultaneously, it must be an effective agent for all who will provide the necessary financial support and

3. Members of the Committee on Preservation and Access are listed in Appendix A.

4. Members of the Commission on Preservation and Access and organizations funding the Commission are listed in Appendix A.

intellectual assistance. Among its early tasks (as outlined in *Brittle Books*), the Commission will be expected to:

1. Develop a funding plan for the preservation of brittle books and, with assistance from the Advisory Council, establish and develop a program to generate funds for use by participating libraries.
2. Establish the general conditions, policies, and procedures governing preservation work for the guidance of libraries, publishers, and other agencies interested in participating in the brittle books program.
3. Promote further development of a preservation information service by the Library of Congress and, especially, encourage the members of the Advisory Council to bring such information to the attention of their own organizations.
4. Encourage technical and other research on topics of importance to the brittle books program. Leadership of and cooperation among the national libraries and the National Archives seems especially critical in this area.
5. Establish a monitoring system to gather and analyze information about all aspects of preservation activity. Results of analytical work will help shape future methods and directions, will keep participants informed, and will be required in the preparation of reports to funding sources.
6. Monitor the performance of bibliographic systems to assure that information required to manage the preservation enterprise and to promote access to products is readily available.
7. Assure that access to preserved materials is efficient and supportive of research and scholarship. It is probable that existing practices and procedures will have to be modified as the quantity of available items increases.
8. Build and maintain effective communication with key organizations through the Advisory Council and promote participation in planning and operations by institutions and individuals committed to the cause of preservation.

In the course of its work, the original Committee on Preservation and Access initiated several research projects. Robert Hayes was commissioned to establish a stronger factual base concerning collection condition, collection overlap, and anticipated benefits of a collaborative preservation program. His study is scheduled for completion by June 1987. A second research project, undertaken by Paul Kantor, is a detailed study of the efficiency and costs of microfilm operations in several settings.

The need to preserve library materials, while well understood in the library community, has received little general attention. To raise awareness of the

importance of the issue, a documentary film—sponsored by CLR, the Library of Congress, and the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH)—is being produced for public television broadcast. A shorter version of the film will be made available for audiences in universities, public libraries, schools, and other interested organizations. Funding for the film was provided by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, NEH, and the Council.

Because preservation is an international problem, CLR helped fund a conference for representatives from more than thirty national libraries, held in Vienna in April 1986. Participants considered the national and international aspects of preservation and the prospects for collaborative work.

To curtail preservation problems in the future, CLR continues to encourage efforts to have scholarly works published on acid-free paper. Building on earlier CLR work, a standard for permanent and durable uncoated paper has been established, and funding has been provided to develop a national standard for bindings.

Resources and Preservation Projects, 1985/1986

American Film Foundation

For a study leading to a brief report, full outline, and comprehensive budget for production of a film on the preservation of library and archival materials.

American Film Foundation

To produce a film on the preservation of library and archival materials.

American Film Foundation

To produce a half-hour version of the preservation film.

American Library Association

To partially fund expenses of speakers for a series of conferences on the preservation of library materials, sponsored by the Resources and Technical Services Division of ALA in cooperation with the Library of Congress.

Gary W. Collins

To develop a plan for an optical disk life expectancy program to be carried out at the Library of Congress.

Duke University

To collect information on the construction of Byzantine bindings and to make comparisons with other early bookbinding practices.

Robert M. Hayes

To obtain data relating to the costs of preservation and overlap of collections in several Association of Research Libraries member libraries.

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions

To help plan new core programs, including preservation and Universal Access to Publications, and to establish a management structure for those programs.

The Library of Congress

To help fund travel costs, translation services, and a rapporteur for the Conference of Directors of National Libraries' Conference on Preservation of Library Materials held in Vienna, April 7–10, 1986.

National Information Standards Organization

For development of an American National Standard for hard cover edition bindings.

Tantalus Inc.

To study preservation microfilming in four libraries, including assessment of cost determination, task analysis/job design, and quality control.

Program Activities, 1985/1986**Committee on Preservation and Access**

November 22, 1985 (Washington, D.C.)

Subcommittee on the Scholar's Role in the Preservation of Library Resources

October 2, 1985 (Washington, D.C.)

Forum III

March 19–21, 1986 (Wye Plantation, Maryland)

Mid-Atlantic States Cooperative Preservation Service

March 31, 1986 (New York Historical Society)

Commission on Preservation and Access

April 29, 1986 (Washington, D.C.)

Bibliographic Services

While CLR interest in bibliographic matters remains strong, the special Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP) is drawing to a close as libraries and networks begin to implement system linkages. By early 1986, the Linked Systems Project (LSP) had developed to the point that it was practical to establish two new committees to manage the project's transition to operational status. The LSP Policy Committee will address management issues that arise as implementation proceeds; membership includes adminis-

trative officers of the four LSP participants, OCLC Online Computer Library Center, the Library of Congress (LC), The Research Libraries Group (RLG), and the Western Library Network (WLN); a representative from the RLG and OCLC memberships; and the chairman of the Technical Committee (see below).⁵ The committee has approved agreements that will guide future development work and serve as the basis for the program's governance and financial structure. These agreements include a formal statement that the LSP protocols will be the protocols of the International Standards Organization/Open Systems Interconnection (ISO/OSI) and/or National Information Standards Organization (NISO) Committee Z39; a list, in order of priority, of work yet to be done in the context of LSP; and the assumptions and ground rules that will guide the exchange of authority and bibliographic data via the link.

The LSP Technical Committee was established to monitor the implementation and performance of the LSP protocols. The committee also will encourage and expedite extended use of the protocols by sharing information and resources. Its members represent the LSP participants, system vendors, and national agencies that support LSP development.

The telecommunications link has been successfully tested by all LSP participants. Authority records have been transmitted from LC to the Research Libraries Information Network (RLIN) for several months, and work on authorities implementation continues. In a related project, the Triangle Research Libraries Network is creating a link for bibliographic record exchange between its local database and OCLC's union catalog.

The Automation Vendor Interface Advisory Committee, representing system vendors interested in implementing the LSP protocol and developing new applications, was organized in June 1985. It has met with the Policy Committee and the Technical Committee to learn about LSP, and will assess LSP specifications and make recommendations to its constituents regarding additional applications.

The Association of American Publishers' project to create codes for manuscripts in electronic form completed the bulk of its work during the year. A provisional standard was published and presented to ISO and NISO in 1986. The *Author's Guide*, *Reference Manual on Electronic Manuscript Preparation and Markup*, *Markup of Mathematical Formulas*, and *Markup of Tabular Material* have also been completed and are available for purchase.

The Association of Research Libraries' (ARL) plan for North American retrospective conversion of bibliographic records is being implemented. The project, designed to identify and coordinate new retrospective conversion projects with existing efforts, involved over thirty member libraries in planning and proposing projects in subject areas such as technology, Slavic studies, agriculture, and Latin American studies. The Associated Music

5. Members of the BSDP Program Committee (which completed its work in 1985), the LSP Policy Committee, and the LSP Technical Committee are listed in Appendix A.

Libraries Group's (AMLG) pilot project for retrospective conversion of research materials in music involves inputting records into OCLC's database as a part of this plan. OCLC and RLG have agreed to a no-cost tape exchange of records created in these projects.

In January the Council sponsored a conference to review the results of research undertaken by OCLC and Forest Press to investigate the effectiveness of the Dewey Decimal Classification schedules and relative index as subject access enhancements to online catalogs. Participants concluded that the DDC may be useful in enhancing subject access under certain circumstances. The project also generated additional information concerning the ways in which users interact with online catalogs.

ARL's CONSER A&I project has been completed. The purposes of this work were to identify abstracting and indexing services that index specific titles and to add that information to CONSER bibliographic records.

Bibliographic Services Projects, 1985/1986

Association of American Publishers

To develop standard codes for identifying components of manuscripts in electronic form, building on past work by the Graphic Communications Association, the American National Standards Institute, and the International Standards Organization.

Association of Research Libraries

To develop a coordinated North American retrospective conversion program.

Columbia University

For a study to measure the impact of online public access catalog implementation on all aspects of public services at the Columbia University Libraries.

Forest Press

In conjunction with the OCLC Online Computer Library Center, to explore the use of the Dewey Decimal Classification as a subject access enhancement for online catalogs.

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions

For consultative assistance in modifying the MINISIS management and information retrieval software at Canada's International Development Research Center to support Universal MARC (UNIMARC), the standard communications format for bibliographic records adopted by IFLA. The product will enable many institutions in developing countries to process UNIMARC cards.

Linked Systems Project

Participants: The Library of Congress, the OCLC Online Computer Library Center, The Research Libraries Group, and the Western Library Network.

To design, develop, test, and implement a standardized telecommunication link, or Standard Network Interconnection, to permit exchange of data, initially between the LC, OCLC, RLG, and WLN computer systems and, ultimately, between any two computer systems.

To implement the exchange of authority records, using the Standard Network Interconnection.

To analyze requirements and develop additional functional specifications for the online exchange of bibliographic records and related information, using communication links developed in the Linked Systems Project.

National Information Standards Organization

To support service as secretariat for International Standards Organization Technical Committee 46 (Documentation), Subcommittee 4 (Automation in Documentation).

OCLC Online Computer Library Center

In conjunction with Forest Press, to explore the use of the Dewey Decimal Classification as a subject access enhancement for online catalogs.

OCLC Online Computer Library Center

For partial support for work to develop OCLC's Linked Systems Project communications interface and software for the authorities application.

OHIONET

To develop and test an online subject thesaurus that links Library of Congress Subject Headings with Dewey Decimal and Library of Congress Classification numbers.

Stanford University

To investigate end-user searching of bibliographic databases by comparing the effectiveness and costs of using the DIALOG command language with the Institute for Scientific Information's Sci-Mate intermediary software.

University of California, Berkeley

To cover programming costs for a database of full text transcriptions and bibliographic records of Italian lyric poetry and associated music, 1450–1650.

University of California, Los Angeles

To conduct a workshop on philosophical concepts underlying descriptive cataloging.

University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign

To develop and evaluate online catalog interface enhancements that will provide expanded subject access to library collections through external databases.

University of Kentucky Research Foundation

To enable Lois M. Chan to revise her text, *Library of Congress Subject Headings: Principles and Application*, adding material on changes influenced by AACR2 and a study of LC subject headings in online public access catalogs. The second edition was published in 1986.

University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill

For the development of protocols for the exchange of bibliographic records by the Triangle Research Libraries Network and OCLC.

Program Activities 1985/1986

Bibliographic Service Development Program Committee
September 5–6, 1985 (Washington, D.C.)

Bibliographic Service Development Program Linked Systems Project
Policy Committee
December 9, 1985 (Washington, D.C.)
February 6, 1986 (Washington, D.C.)
April 29, 1986 (Minneapolis, Minnesota)

Technical Committee
July 6, 1985 (Chicago, Illinois)
August 26, 1985 (San Francisco, California)
November 20, 1985 (Washington, D.C.)
March 11, 1986 (Chicago, Illinois)
June 27, 1986 (New York City)

Network Advisory Committee
December 9–11, 1985 (Washington, D.C.)
March 12–14, 1986 (Washington, D.C.)

Adding Specifications for Three-Dimensional Objects to the USMARC
Materials Format
April 8, 1986 (Washington, D.C.)

USMARC Format Extensions for Preservation
May 15–16, 1986 (Washington, D.C.)

Access

Providing equitable access to information is one of the primary responsibilities of libraries. As user requirements increase in depth and diversity, the assignment grows increasingly difficult because the obligation holds for the obscure as well as the routine. The Council's activities in this arena are necessarily diffused; considerations pertinent to the goal of equitable access permeate every CLR activity—research, preservation, bibliographic systems, and librarianship itself. Special support from the Ford Foundation permits CLR to explore access-related issues on many fronts.

The principles set forth in CLR's statement, "Scholarship, Research, and Access to Information," are pursued at every opportunity.⁶ Several small grants have been made to permit exploration of technological approaches to enhancing access to information, to examine the quality and coverage of databases, and to measure the influence of library policies and procedures on access.

CLR also is encouraging the librarians of historically black colleges to consider prospects for utilizing more fully technology-based information systems to improve their services and to open to their constituents previously unavailable resources. Stimulated by the same objective, CLR is encouraging public libraries to assess the present and potential influence of computer-based information resources on services to users. In the final analysis, the goal of equitable access to information is an appropriate driving force behind collaborative undertakings of libraries. The success of all such ventures ultimately must be measured by how they improve services to users.

Access Projects, 1985/1986

American Geographical Society

To plan for a new *Columbia Gazetteer of the World*.

American Library Association

To help defray expenses associated with the August 1985 International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions Conference and associated meetings.

Association of Academic Health Sciences Library Directors

To partially fund a joint AAHSLD/Medical Library Association project to produce guidelines for academic health sciences center libraries. *Challenges to Action: Planning and Evaluation Guidelines for Academic Health Sciences Libraries* was published in January 1986.

6. Council on Library Resources, Inc. *Twenty-ninth Annual Report* (Washington, D.C. 1985), 36–38.

Carleton College

To cover in part the costs for producing a second volume of Ann Niles' *An Index to Microform Collections*.

Center for Research Libraries

To engage a consultant to assist the Center in studying its membership, governance, and fees structures.

International Council for Scientific and Technical Information

To compare the use of serials by major interlibrary loan organizations in the United States, France, and the United Kingdom.

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions

To work with other organizations to follow up recommendations contained in *Copyright and Library Materials for the Handicapped* (1981).

Northern Illinois University

To partially cover the costs of publication of a guide to rare and out-of-print books in the Vatican Film Library.

The Research Libraries Group, Inc.

For partial travel costs for Library of Congress personnel attending the RLG Archives, Manuscripts and Special Collections Task Force meetings.

The Research Libraries Group, Inc.

To coordinate a project to create a national database of descriptions of state government records within the Research Libraries Information Network.

The Research Libraries Group, Inc.

To analyze the RLG Collections Conspectus as a management tool.

University of California, Los Angeles

To enable John V. Richardson, Jr., to begin work on an annotated bibliography of English-language works about education for librarianship.

University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign

To enable William Gray Potter to study collection overlap and diversity in Illinois academic libraries using the Library Computer System.

University of Kentucky Research Foundation

To enable Lois M. Chan to compile a bibliographic guide to indexing languages used in online bibliographic databases.

University of Michigan

To examine attitudes of faculty in selected disciplines concerning shelving books in storage facilities and to test the influence of enhanced access and delivery services on those attitudes.

University of Pittsburgh

To enable Anne Woodsworth to investigate the role and organizational relationships of information managers in universities.

Priscilla C. Yu

Partial assistance for a study of collection development in Western language materials in selected Chinese academic and research libraries.

Program Activities, 1985/1986

Participation by Large Research Libraries in the RLG Program
September 26, 1985 (Washington, D.C.)

Information Access in Historically Black Colleges
April 21–22, 1986 (Atlanta, Ga.)

Librarianship and Librarians

The transition to the research library projected for the future will require librarians of diverse backgrounds and knowledge. How to prepare the new leadership is a persistent and still unanswered question. The Council has supported program explorations and development in several library schools and is now preparing for an assessment of results and possible redirection of its professional education activities.

CLR support for the University of Michigan library school's program designed to recruit distinctive students possessing analytic and quantitative skills from liberal arts colleges drew to a close as the University assumed responsibility for continuing the effort. The library and library school are working together to recruit students to academic librarianship and to provide a productive internship as an integral part of the educational program.

A third group of Senior Fellows attended the intensive academic session at the University of California, Los Angeles, library school in August 1985. Plans have been approved to continue the program for newly appointed library directors and top-level managers for two more sessions, with UCLA and participants assuming an increasing proportion of the cost each year.

The funds earmarked for library school planning grants have been exhausted. Fifteen awards were made under this program and three institutions have received implementation grants: the University of Wisconsin, Madison, the University of Chicago, and Louisiana State University.

In the summer of 1985, the University of Georgia Libraries and a group of libraries in the Chicago area (University of Chicago; University of Illinois, Chicago; and Northwestern University) began internship programs for staff who were recent library school graduates. The internships, in each case, were designed to bring the new librarians into closer contact with the complexities and opportunities of scholarship and university operations. Fifteen librarians participated in the first series of seminars, discussions, classes, and visits to other institutions. In the spring of 1986, two more internship program grants were awarded: one to the University of Missouri, Columbia, and one to Columbia University. One or two additional programs will be considered during the coming year.

Jeffrey Horrell of Dartmouth College was selected as a CLR Management Intern. Mr. Horrell will begin a nine-month internship with David Stam at Syracuse University beginning in September 1986.

The cooperative research grant program continues to provide opportunities for librarians and teaching faculty to work together on topics of importance to academic libraries. Proposals increase in number each year; ten awards were made in the two cycles of 1985/86. A descriptive brochure was prepared and distributed in the summer of 1986.

Professional Education Projects, 1985/1986

Association of Research Libraries

To enable the Office of Management Studies to design and conduct a second Institute for Library Educators.

Catholic University of America

To partially fund an American Library Association-International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) First World Conference on Continuing Library and Information Science Education, held as a preconference to the 1985 IFLA meetings.

Columbia University

To plan a Library Fellows Program that will provide substantive orientation for librarians new to the profession and the research library environment.

Indiana University

To plan a continuing education program for librarians on issues of importance to research libraries and their users.

Indiana University

To commission three papers for a forum on research librarianship for Indiana University librarians and School of Library and Information Science faculty.

Louisiana State University

To implement a multi-disciplinary curriculum for library systems analysts.

P. B. Mangla

To cover the direct costs of visiting selected libraries and library schools in the U.S. following the IFLA Conference.

North Carolina Central University

To plan an interdisciplinary master's degree program in information science.

Ohio University

To partially cover publication costs for the proceedings of the 1983 joint meeting of the Chinese-American Library Association and the Asian/Pacific American Librarians Association.

University of California, Los Angeles

To continue the Senior Fellows Program, which provides senior library administrators with opportunities for intensive, specialized study in management, and independent research.

University of California, Los Angeles

To explore the potential for a coordinated degree program between the School of Library and Information Science and the College of Fine Arts.

University of Chicago

For a multi-institutional internship program for recently hired library school graduates. Those involved are the University of Chicago Library and Graduate Library School, Northwestern University Libraries, and the University of Illinois at Chicago Library.

University of Chicago

To implement a special concentration in library automation and information systems and stimulate awareness of the program within the university and library communities.

University of Georgia

To develop an internship program to introduce recently hired library school graduates to the full range of issues important to the university and to librarianship generally.

University of Michigan

To provide fellowship funding for the School of Library Science's program to prepare specially recruited students for leadership roles in academic/research libraries.

University of Michigan

To build a cooperative academic/internship program for library school students between the University Library and the Library School.

University of Missouri, Columbia

To establish a postgraduate internship program for librarians new to the profession.

University of Wisconsin, Madison

To implement a two-year academic program to enhance research librarians'

problem recognition and problem solving capabilities through training in research methods.

Faculty/Librarian Cooperative Research Projects 1982–1985 Grants Active in Fiscal 1986

Ruth Person, Catholic University, and George Charles Newman, State University of New York at Buffalo

To study the selection process for university library directors.

Katherine Chiang, Howard Curtis, Linda Stewart, and J. Robert Cooke, Cornell University

To test the use of microcomputer technology for supporting access to large bibliographic data files and to make a MEDLARS database subset available to users.

Sara Woolpy and Jerome H. Woolpy, Earlham College

To study the use of online abstracts as a source of information for undergraduate research.

David Vidor and Elizabeth Futas, Emory University

To study collection development in professional school collections.

Marcy Murphy, Indiana University, and Martha Bailey, Purdue University

To identify managerial competencies at four professional levels in research libraries.

Carolyn Snyder, George Whitbeck, and Stella Bentley, Indiana University

To study the costs of public services in research libraries.

Merrill W. Smith and Patrick A. Purcell, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

To examine the electronic delivery of visual images and text from the library to the academic community.

Andrew Torok and Jitka Hurych, Northern Illinois University

To study online searching of bibliographic and numeric databases.

Lloyd Davidson, Northwestern University, and Julie Hurd, University of Chicago

To analyze Chemical Abstracts Service online end user transaction logs and user behavior.

Marjorie Murfin, Ohio State University, and Charles Bunge, University of Wisconsin

To analyze survey data for an assessment of reference services.

Thomas T. Surprenant, Queens College, Barbara Moran, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, and Merrily Taylor, Brown University

To explore the role of the library in Brown University's efforts to incorporate electronic technologies in teaching, learning, and research.

Arthur Downing and Daniel O'Connor, Rutgers University

To study undergraduates' preferences for the number of bibliographic citations obtained through online searching.

Helen Gotthberg and Donald Riggs, University of Arizona

To study time management in academic libraries.

Julia Gelfand and John King, University of California, Irvine

To study the effects of consolidation in a university library, economies of scale, and services to multi-disciplinary research units.

Mary Biggs, University of Chicago, and Victor Biggs, Lake Forest College

To study collection development policies for academic library reference collections.

Betty Taylor, Elizabeth Mann, and Robert J. Munro, University of Florida

To study the impact of automation on the law school library budget, and the implications for library budgeting in general.

Kathleen Gunning, University of Houston, and Carolyn Frost, University of Michigan

To explore requirements for making subject access via Library of Congress subject headings more comprehensible to online catalog users.

Beverly P. Lynch and Jo Ann Verdin, University of Illinois at Chicago

To replicate an investigation of the nature of the work of university libraries, and assess the impact of technological change on organizational structure, task characteristics, communication patterns, unit output, and job satisfaction.

Helen Lloyd Snoke and Jean T. Loup, University of Michigan

For a comparison of the approval plan profiles of academic research libraries.

Robert Swisher and Rosemary Du Mont, University of Oklahoma, and Calvin Boyer, University of California, Irvine

To study the extent to which female academic/research librarians seek administrative positions.

Mark Rorvig, Siegfried Rempel, George Wead, Francis Miksa, Bernard Lukenbill, and Timothy Whelan, University of Texas

To measure users' preferences for bibliographic records that include photographs or other representations of nonbook items.

Merwin Lewis, M. Elizabeth Dolan, and Alexis J. Jamieson, University of Western Ontario

To survey users' experiences with remote access to online library systems.

Charles A. Bunge, University of Wisconsin, Madison, and Marjorie Murfin, Ohio State University

To refine computer readable forms and develop interpretative materials for gathering data on reference questions in academic/research libraries.

James Sweetland, University of Wisconsin, Milwaukee, and Darlene Weingand, University of Wisconsin, Madison

To study the use of transaction fees on the use of interlibrary loan services.

1985/1986 Grants

Michael L. Tomlan and Judith Holliday, Cornell University

To search for certain nineteenth-century American architectural periodicals held outside research libraries.

Marianne Cooper and Shoshana Kaufmann, Queens College of the City University of New York

To examine the relationships between library schools and academic libraries in the same institutions, and identify factors that encourage or hinder development of cooperative efforts.

Richard S. Halsey and Ruth Fraley, State University of New York, Albany

To conduct a market study of the information needs of scholars in public affairs and policy departments at Rockefeller College, SUNY-Albany.

Nancy B. Nuzzo and William E. McGrath, State University of New York, Buffalo

To validate statistically the Research Libraries Group Collections Conceptus for music.

Neil Yerkey and Maryruth Glogowski, State University of New York, Buffalo

To determine how citations relevant to library and information science are scattered among machine-readable bibliographic databases.

Carolyn O. Frost and Bonnie A. Dede, University of Michigan

To test subject heading compatibility between the Library of Congress Subject Headings and the University Library's catalog for automated authority control.

Rosie Albritton and Mary Ellen Sievert, University of Missouri, Columbia

To explore the effects of staff attitudes toward computer technology on their levels of participation in a library computer literacy program.

Mark Rorvig, Allison Beck, and David Gracy, University of Texas, Austin

To create a digitized, facsimile version of the political cartoons in the Jesse Holman Jones papers and measure users' reactions to the product.

James H. Sweetland and Wilfred Fong, University of Wisconsin, Milwaukee

To evaluate the effects of book reviews on library purchasing decisions.

Ralph A. Gustafson, Ronald J. Chepesiuk, and Gloria Kelley, Winthrop College

To evaluate the effectiveness of several chemicals against mold growth (mildew) in library collections.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

To help outstanding individuals broaden their experience and enhance their management skills through nine-month internships at research libraries. ***Jeffrey Horrell***, Dartmouth College, was selected as the 1985-86 intern. He is working with David Stam, Syracuse University Library.

Program Activities, 1985/1986

Administrators of Internships for Recent Graduates Program
June 28, 1986 (New York City)

Academic Library Management Intern Program Selection Committee
January 31 and February 10, 1986 (Washington, D.C.)

Appendix A

Program Committees and Project Participants

RESEARCH ADVISORY PANEL

Richard Bulliet
*Professor of History and Director,
Middle East Institute
Columbia University*

John Coatsworth
*Professor of History
University of Chicago
(Resigned, May 1986)*

Lawrence Cremin
*Frederick A. P. Barnard Professor
of Education
Teachers College, Columbia
University;
President, The Spencer Foundation*

Herbert Morton
*Director, Office of Scholarly
Communication and Technology
American Council of Learned
Societies*

Brian Perry
*Director, Research and Development
Division
The British Library*

Seymour Pollack
*Professor of Computer Science
Washington University*

Henry Riecken
*Associate Director for Planning and
Evaluation
National Library of Medicine*

William Schaefer
*Executive Vice Chancellor
University of California,
Los Angeles*

Basil Stuart-Stubbs
*Director, School of Library,
Archival, and Information
Studies
University of British Columbia*

Robert Warner
*Dean, School of Information and
Library Studies
University of Michigan*

William Welsh
Deputy Librarian of Congress

**BIBLIOGRAPHIC SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM
PROGRAM COMMITTEE**

Henriette Avram <i>Library of Congress</i>	Carol Ishimoto <i>Harvard University</i>
Rowland Brown <i>OCLC Online Computer Library Center</i>	Frederick Kilgour <i>OCLC Online Computer Library Center</i>
Joan Gotwals <i>University of Pennsylvania</i>	Richard McCoy <i>The Research Libraries Group, Inc.</i>
James Govan <i>University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill</i>	Roderick Swartz <i>Washington State Library (Deceased, February 1986)</i>

**BIBLIOGRAPHIC SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM
LINKED SYSTEMS PROJECT**

LSP POLICY COMMITTEE

Henriette Avram <i>Library of Congress</i>	Mary Ellen Jacob <i>OCLC Online Computer Library Center</i>
David Bishop <i>University of Georgia</i>	Richard McCoy <i>The Research Libraries Group, Inc.</i>
Rowland Brown <i>OCLC Online Computer Library Center</i>	N. A. Stussy <i>Western Library Network</i>
Richard Dougherty <i>University of Michigan</i>	Nancy Zussy <i>Western Library Network</i>
Dorothy Gregor <i>University of California, San Diego</i>	

LSP TECHNICAL COMMITTEE

David Bishop (Chair) <i>University of Georgia</i>	Ray Denenberg <i>Library of Congress</i>
James Aagaard <i>Northwestern University Library</i>	Ahmed El-Hoshy <i>National Library of Medicine</i>
Richard Adrion <i>National Science Foundation</i>	Larry Learn <i>OCLC Online Computer Library Center</i>
Edwin Buchinski <i>National Library of Canada</i>	Michael Monahan <i>GEAC Computers International, Inc.</i>
Tom Brown <i>Western Library Network</i>	Jeanne Sawyer <i>Triangle Research Libraries Network</i>
Wayne Davison <i>The Research Libraries Group, Inc.</i>	

COMMISSION ON PRESERVATION AND ACCESS

Millicent Abell <i>Yale University</i>	Kenneth Gros Louis <i>Indiana University</i>
Herbert Bailey <i>Princeton University Press</i>	Carole Huxley <i>New York State Education Department</i>
Billy Frye <i>Emory University</i>	Sidney Verba <i>Harvard University</i>
James Govan <i>University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill</i>	William Welsh <i>Library of Congress</i>
Vartan Gregorian <i>New York Public Library</i>	

The Commission on Preservation and Access was formed in the spring of 1986 to continue the work of the CLR Committee on Preservation and Access. While the Commission is an independent body, CLR is providing financial and administrative support during the Commission's formative period. Funding for the first three years of the Commission's work is being provided by CLR, the H. W. Wilson Foundation, and the following:

Columbia University
Yale University
Indiana University
University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign
University of Michigan
Princeton University
Harvard University
Stanford University

Participants in the New York State Preservation Program

COMMITTEE ON PRESERVATION AND ACCESS

Billy Frye, Chair

Emory University

Harold Billings

University of Texas, Austin

Carole Huxley

*New York State Education
Department*

Peter Likins

Lehigh University

Herbert Morton

*Office of Scholarly Communication
and Technology
American Council of Learned Societies*

Robert O'Neil

University of Virginia

Rutherford Rogers

*Former University Librarian
Yale University*

Neil Rudenstine

Princeton University

Peter Sparks

Library of Congress

David Stam

Syracuse University

Sidney Verba

Harvard University

Robert Warner

University of Michigan

Bernice Wenzel

*University of California,
Los Angeles*

Observers: Harold Cannon

National Endowment for the Humanities

John Vaughn

Association of American Universities

Consultant: Margaret Child

SEMINAR ON THE ECONOMICS OF RESEARCH LIBRARIES
OCTOBER 1985

Barry Adams

Cornell University

Patricia Battin

Columbia University

Michael Cooper

University of California, Berkeley

Richard De Gennaro

University of Pennsylvania

Billy Frye

Emory University

Malcolm Getz

Vanderbilt University

Robert Gillespie

Gillespie, Folkner & Associates

Maurice Glicksman

Brown University

Robert Hayes

University of California, Los Angeles

William Hubbard, Jr.

Upjohn Company

Ray Hunt, Jr.

University of Virginia

James Hyatt

*National Association of
College and University
Business Officers*

Herbert Johnson

Emory University

Paul Kantor

Tantalus Inc.

Charles McClure

Syracuse University

Richard Talbot

University of Massachusetts

Lawrence White

New York University

Appendix B

Publications and Reports Resulting From CLR Programs, 1985–1986

Part I. Publications of the Council and CLR Staff

Committee on Preservation and Access. *Brittle Books: Reports of the Committee on Preservation and Access*. Washington, D.C., Council on Library Resources, 1986.

"Council on Library Resources Research Grants" (brochure). February 1986.

Cummings, Martin M. "Economics and the Future of Research Libraries." In *International Librarianship Today and Tomorrow*, edited by Joseph W. Price and Mary S. Price, 35–42. New York, K. G. Saur, 1985.

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Haas, Warren J. "New Wine, New Bottles." In *International Librarianship Today and Tomorrow*, edited by Joseph W. Price and Mary S. Price, 53–64. New York, K. G. Saur, 1985.

Online Catalog Screen Displays. Report of a conference sponsored by the Council on Library Resources at the Lakeway Conference Center, Austin, Texas, March 10–13, 1985. Edited by Joan Frye Wil-

liams. Washington, D.C., Council on Library Resources, June 1986.

Rosenberg, Jane A. "The Council on Library Resources, Inc." In *The Bowker Annual of Library and Book Trade Information*, 31st ed., 235–41. New York, Bowker, 1986.

Part II. Publications by Grantees and Contractors

Association of Academic Health Sciences Library Directors. *Challenge to Action: Planning and Evaluation Guidelines for Academic Health Sciences Libraries*. Washington, D.C., Association of Academic Health Sciences Library Directors/Medical Library Association Joint Task Force to Develop Guidelines for Academic Health Sciences Libraries, January 1986.

Association of American Publishers. Electronic Manuscript Project. *Basic Author's Guide to Electronic Manuscript Preparation and Markup*. Washington, D.C., AAP, March 1986.

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———. *Markup of Tabular Material*.

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- . *Reference Manual on Electronic Manuscript Preparation and Markup*. Washington, D.C., AAP, May 1986.
- . *Standard for Electronic Preparation and Markup*. Washington, D.C., AAP, February 1986.
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- D'Elia, George, and Charla Hutkins. "Faculty Use of Document Delivery Services: The Results of a Survey." *Journal of Academic Librarianship* 12 (May 1986) 69–74.
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- Swisher, Robert, Rosemary Ruhig DuMont, and Calvin Boyer. "The Motivation to Manage: A Study of Academic Librarians and Library Science Students." *Library Trends* 34 (Fall 1985) 219-34.
- Universities, Information Technology, and Academic Libraries*. Edited by Robert M. Hayes. Norwood, N.J., Ablex Publishing Corporation, 1986. (Frontiers Conference I)

Part III. Project Reports Received

- Bunge, Charles A., and Marjorie E. Murfin. "Project to Develop Computer Readable Reference Question Data Forms: Narrative Report." January 1986. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Center for Research Libraries. "Final Grant Project Report on the Membership, Governance, and Fees Structure Study." Chicago, Ill., March 31, 1986.
- Gothberg, Helen M., and Donald E. Riggs. "Time Management Study

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- Hurych, Jitka, and Andrew Torok. "Identification and Analysis of Factors Affecting End Use Online Searching." DeKalb, Ill., January 1986. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Jamieson, Alexis J., and M. Elizabeth Dolan. "University Library Experience with Remote Access to Online Catalogs." November 1985. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Kent, A. K., K. Merry, and D. Russon. "The Use of Serials in Document Delivery Systems in Europe and the USA." Paris, International Council for Scientific and Technical Information, February 1986.
- Murfin, Marjorie E. "Reference Assessment Survey Project for the Period July 1, 1984–March 21, 1985." Columbus, Ohio State University Research Foundation, January 1986.
- Murphy, Marcy, and Martha J. Bailey. "An Investigation of the Managerial Competencies of Research Librarians." January 1986. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Sweetland, James, and Darlene Weingand. "The Effect of Transaction Fees on Interlibrary Loan Traffic." 1986. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Trochim, Mary Kane. *Measuring the Book Circulation Use of a Small Academic Library Collection: A Manual*. Washington, D.C., Office of Management Studies, Association of Research Libraries, 1985.
- Vidor, David L., and Elizabeth Furtas. "Collection Development in Professional School Collections." May 1, 1986. (Cooperative Research Project Report)

Appendix C

Program Guidelines and Grant Application Procedures

The Council on Library Resources supports work by individuals and organizations on matters pertinent to library service and information systems, with the primary objective of improving the quality and performance of academic and research libraries. Individuals with specific interests and expertise are encouraged to take the initiative and propose for consideration projects within the broad area of the Council's program, as described in this report.

In addition, CLR sponsors special programs such as that offering support for cooperative research projects involving librarians and teaching faculty. Such programs are described in brochures available from CLR.

Application Procedures

Initial inquiries should state the purpose of the proposed work, identify the methods to be used, establish the credentials of the responsible individuals, and provide a careful estimate of total costs and funding requirements. CLR will respond promptly with an indication of interest. If subsequent exploration seems justified, preparation of a complete proposal will be suggested. Full documentation should include:

1. A fifty-word description of the proposed project.
2. A full explanation of the work to be done, including objectives, duration, and methods to be employed. Background information and the methods proposed for project evaluation should also be included.
3. A detailed project budget in which costs are linked to the tasks to be performed. CLR does not fund indirect costs or equipment purchases.
4. Curricula vitae of the principal investigators.

All proposals are carefully reviewed by CLR staff and external advisors, who consider such matters as relevance to current CLR interests and activities; relationship to other, similar work; projected costs in the context of the work required; and importance of anticipated results. The Council also looks for

institutional support of a proposed project, as demonstrated by a willingness to share in the costs of the enterprise. With the exception of the special programs noted above, there are no deadlines for grant proposals.

All inquiries should be addressed to Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1785 Massachusetts Ave., N.W., Washington, D.C. 20036.

**ACTIVE PROJECTS
FINANCIAL STATEMENTS**

Introduction

The following pages record grants and contracts active during fiscal year 1986 and, through audited financial reports, provide an overall picture of CLR income and expenditures.

The foundations that funded CLR during 1985/1986 are listed below. As we have for each of the past thirty years, we acknowledge their help and offer the thanks of the academic and research library community.

The Carnegie Corporation of New York
The Exxon Education Foundation
The Ford Foundation
The J. Paul Getty Trust
The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation
The Lilly Endowment, Inc.
The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation
The Pew Memorial Trust
The Alfred P. Sloan Foundation
The H. W. Wilson Foundation

Grants and Contracts Active in Fiscal 1986 (unaudited)

	FY 1986			
	Unpaid 6/30/85	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/86
American Film Foundation				
Santa Monica, Calif.				
Planning for a film on the preservation of library materials	\$ -0-	\$ 30,000 (546)	\$ 29,454	\$ -0-
Production of a documentary film on the preservation of library materials	-0-	320,000	160,000	160,000
Thirty-minute version of the preservation film	-0-	25,000	8,500	16,500
American Geographical Society				
New York, N.Y.				
Planning for a new <i>Columbia Gazetteer of the World</i>	7,500	-0-	-0-	7,500
American Library Association				
Chicago, Ill.				
Delegate assistance for 51st IFLA Conference	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Supplementary support for 51st IFLA Conference	-0-	4,000	4,000	-0-
Association of Academic Health Sciences Library Directors				
Washington, D.C.				
Guidelines for academic health sciences center libraries	2,300	-0-	2,300	-0-
Association of American Publishers				
Washington, D.C.				
Development of publishing industry standards and author guidelines for electronic manuscript preparation	10,000	-0-	10,000	-0-

	FY 1986			
	Unpaid 6/30/85	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/86
Association of Research Libraries				
Washington, D.C.				
Development of a coordinated retrospective conversion program	1,395	-0-	1,395	-0-
Institute for library educators Second-1986	25,857	-0-	20,000	5,857
Carleton College				
Northfield, Minn.				
<i>Index to Microform Collections,</i> Volume 2	-0-	300	-0-	300
Catholic University of America				
Washington, D.C.				
Conference on continuing library and information science education	5,000	-0-	5,000	-0-
Center for Research Libraries				
Chicago, Ill.				
Study of membership, governance, and fees	800	-0-	800	-0-
Gary W. Collins				
Boulder, Colo.				
Development of a plan for a Library of Congress optical disk life determination program	-0-	15,000	15,000	-0-
Columbia University				
New York, N.Y.				
Library fellows program	-0-	44,450	-0-	44,450
Measuring the public services impact of an online catalog	11,200	-0-	-0-	11,200
Cornell University				
Ithaca, N.Y.				
Locating 19th century American architectural periodicals	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Testing microcomputer technology to support access to large bibliographic data files	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-

	FY 1986			Unpaid 6/30/86
	Unpaid 6/30/85	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Duke University				
Durham, N.C.				
Research on Byzantine bindings	2,500	(2,500)	-0-	-0-
Earlham College				
Richmond, Ind.				
Use of online abstracts for undergraduate research	1,267	-0-	1,267	-0-
Forest Press				
Albany, N.Y.				
The Dewey Decimal Classification as an online searching tool for subject access	7,350	-0-	7,350	-0-
Robert M. Hayes				
Los Angeles, Calif.				
Study of preservation costs and benefits	-0-	40,100	10,000	30,100
Indiana University				
Bloomington, Ind.				
Papers for a forum series on research librarianship	-0-	5,000	4,000	1,000
International Council for Scientific and Technical Information				
Paris, France				
Comparison of serials usage by interlibrary loan organizations	1,000	-0-	1,000	-0-
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions				
The Hague, Netherlands				
Planning IFLA core programs	67,000	-0-	23,000	44,000
Report on copyright and materials for the handicapped	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000

	FY 1986			
	Unpaid 6/30/85	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/86
Library of Congress				
Washington, D.C.				
Bibliographic analysis—				
Linked Systems Project	3,120	-0-	-0-	3,120
International conference on preservation of library materials	-0-	18,250	16,000	2,250
Louisiana State University				
Baton Rouge, La.				
Development of a curriculum for library systems analysts	-0-	52,000	18,000	34,000
P. B. Mangla				
Delhi, India				
Travel to selected U.S. libraries and library schools	2,500	(820)	2,500 (820)	-0-
Massachusetts Institute of Technology				
Cambridge, Mass.				
Study of electronic delivery of text and visual images from the library to the academic community	2,894	-0-	2,894	-0-
National Association of College and University Business Officers				
Washington, D.C.				
Study of strategic planning in university libraries	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000
National Information Standards Organization				
Gaithersburg, Md.				
Development of an American national standard for hard cover edition bindings	-0-	25,000	-0-	25,000
Service as secretariat for an International Standards Organization subcommittee	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-

	FY 1986			
	Unpaid 6/30/85	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/86
Northern Illinois University				
DeKalb, Ill.				
Publication of a guide to rare and out-of-print books in the Vatican Film Library	-0-	1,200	1,200	-0-
OCLC Online Computer				
Library Center				
Dublin, Ohio				
Participation in the Linked Systems Project	139,000	-0-	115,000	24,000
OHIONET				
Columbus, Ohio				
Subject thesaurus research for an online catalog	612	(612)	-0-	-0-
Ohio University				
Athens, Ohio				
Publication subvention	1,500	-0-	1,500	-0-
Ruth Person				
Washington, D.C.				
Study of the selection process for university librarians	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000
Queens College				
Flushing, N.Y.				
Examining relationships between library schools and their institutions' libraries	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000
Study of the role of Brown University's library in the implementation of the electronic campus	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-
The Research Libraries				
Group, Inc.				
Stanford, Calif.				
Analysis of the RLG conspectus as a collection management tool	-0-	10,000	-0-	10,000
Bibliographic analysis— Linked Systems Project	11,470	-0-	-0-	11,470

	FY 1986			
	Unpaid 6/30/85	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/86
Creation of a national database of public records information	-0-	32,928 (2,396)	15,000	15,532
Joint project for authorities implementation	89,245	-0-	-0-	89,245
Travel support for RLG archives committee	-0-	5,000	-0-	5,000
Stanford University				
Stanford, Calif.				
Investigation of end-user searching of bibliographic databases	4,300	-0-	-0-	4,300
State University of New York				
Albany, N.Y.				
Study of information needs of public affairs scholars	-0-	2,996	-0-	2,996
State University of New York				
Buffalo, N.Y.				
Investigation of coverage of library and information science in bibliographic databases	-0-	2,935	2,935	-0-
Study of statistical reliability of indicators in the RLG conspectus for music	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000
Tantalus Inc.				
Cleveland, Ohio				
Study of preservation microfilming	-0-	9,670	5,000	4,670
University of California				
Berkeley, Calif.				
Demonstration of a packet radio terminal system	5,000	-0-	5,000	-0-
Programming for a database of transcriptions of Italian poetry and music	-0-	1,200	1,200	-0-

	FY 1986			
	Unpaid 6/30/85	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/86
University of California				
Los Angeles, Calif.				
Bibliography on education for librarianship	1,000	-0-	1,000	-0-
Conference on conceptual foundations of cataloging	-0-	9,670	-0-	9,670
Research program: long-range strategic planning for libraries and information resources in research universities	-0-	400,000	50,000	350,000
Senior fellows program				
1983-86	56,392	-0-	-0-	56,392
1987	-0-	45,000	-0-	45,000
University of Chicago				
Chicago, Ill.				
Implementation of a concentration in library automation and information systems	39,500	-0-	-0-	39,500
Multi-institutional professional development program for recent library school graduates	36,960	-0-	-0-	36,960
University of Georgia				
Athens, Ga.				
Internships for recent library school graduates	80,000	-0-	9,842	70,158
University of Illinois				
Chicago, Ill.				
Study of the impact of technological changes on library units	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-
University of Illinois				
Urbana, Ill.				
Collection development and overlap in the LCS network in Illinois	3,320	(1,627)	(1,627)	3,320

	FY 1986			
	Unpaid 6/30/85	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/86
Developing and evaluating online catalog interface enhancements	-0-	23,000	15,000	8,000
University of Kentucky				
Lexington, Ky.				
Bibliographic guide to indexing languages used in online databases	-0-	5,580	3,000	2,580
Second edition of <i>Library of Congress Subject Headings: Principles and Application</i>	360	(75)	(75)	360
University of Michigan				
Ann Arbor, Mich.				
Basic professional education for research librarianship	77,330	-0-	46,850	30,480
Comparison of approval plan profiles of research libraries	2,935	-0-	2,935	-0-
Examination of subject heading compatibility between a research library catalog and Library of Congress subject headings	-0-	2,995	2,995	-0-
Study of the relationship between bibliographic access to stored materials and faculty attitudes	31,747	(14,884)	-0-	16,863
University Library Associates Program	35,000	-0-	-0-	35,000
University of Minnesota				
St. Paul, Minn.				
Development of a document delivery model	1,127	(212)	915	-0-
University of Missouri				
Columbia, Mo.				
Internships for recent library school graduates	-0-	73,205	18,000	55,205

	FY 1986			Unpaid 6/30/86
	Unpaid 6/30/85	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Investigation of effects of human factors on a library computer literacy program	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
University of North Carolina Chapel Hill, N.C.				
Development of protocols for exchange of bibliographic records	-0-	54,670	25,000	29,670
University of Pittsburgh Pittsburgh, Pa.				
Study of roles of information managers in American universities	-0-	10,990	9,000	1,990
University of Texas at Austin Austin, Tex.				
Analysis of users' interest in digitized images	-0-	2,964	2,964	-0-
University of Wisconsin Madison, Wis.				
Development of a supplementary education program for academic and research librarians	50,563	-0-	29,951	20,612
University of Wisconsin Milwaukee, Wis.				
Study of the effects of published reviews on library purchasing decisions	-0-	2,965	-0-	2,965
Western Library Network Olympia, Wash.				
Bibliographic analysis— Linked Systems Project	6,887	-0-	-0-	6,887
Joint project for authorities implementation	23,801	-0-	-0-	23,801
Winthrop College Rock Hill, S.C.				
Testing chemicals for mildew control in library materials	-0-	2,920	-0-	2,920

	<u>FY 1986</u>			
	Unpaid 6/30/85	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/86
Priscilla C. Yu				
Urbana, Ill.				
Travel and research on collection development in Western language materials in Chinese libraries	100	-0-	100	-0-
Other refunds and adjustments from prior years' grants & contracts	-0-	(2,454)	(2,454)	-0-
Totals	\$864,832	\$1,293,988	\$727,847	\$1,409,823
		(26,126)	(4,976)	

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Opinion of Independent Accountants

August 8, 1986

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying balance sheets and the related statements of revenues, expenses and changes in fund balances, of functional expenses and of changes in cash and short-term investments present fairly the financial position of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1986 and 1985, the results of its operations for the year ended June 30, 1986 and the changes in its cash and short-term investments for the two years then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles consistently applied. Our examinations of these statements were made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

Price Waterhouse
Washington, D.C.

Balance Sheets

	<u>JUNE 30</u>	
	<u>1986</u>	<u>1985</u>
ASSETS		
Cash and short-term investments, including restricted amounts of \$1,705,365 and \$1,271,662, respectively	\$4,362,363	\$3,479,759
Grants receivable (Notes 2 and 5)		
Unrestricted		450,000
Restricted	2,954,164	4,959,000
Prepaid expenses and deposits	<u>6,848</u>	<u>9,821</u>
Total assets	<u>\$7,323,375</u>	<u>\$8,898,580</u>
LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE		
Deferred income (Note 2)		
Unrestricted	\$ 250,000	\$ 700,000
Restricted	3,378,609	5,425,499
Grants and contracts payable (Note 2)		
Unrestricted	128,903	59,669
Restricted	1,280,920	805,163
Accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	40,852	41,321
Federal excise taxes payable		<u>7,108</u>
Total liabilities	<u>5,079,284</u>	<u>7,038,760</u>
Fund balance		
Appropriated	1,441,831	1,156,164
Unappropriated	<u>802,260</u>	<u>703,656</u>
Total fund balance	<u>2,244,091</u>	<u>1,859,820</u>
Total liabilities and fund balance	<u>\$7,323,375</u>	<u>\$8,898,580</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balances

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1986
(With Comparative Totals for 1985)

	Unrestricted	Restricted	Total 1986	Total 1985
Revenues (Note 2)				
Grants and contracts	\$ 450,000	\$1,870,890	\$2,320,890	\$1,878,841
Investment income	<u>282,770</u>	<u> </u>	<u>282,770</u>	<u>355,386</u>
Total revenues	<u>732,770</u>	<u>1,870,890</u>	<u>2,603,660</u>	<u>2,234,227</u>
Expenses (Notes 2, 3 and 4)				
Program				
Research	13,342	613,308	626,650	285,590
Library operations				
Resources	14,609	748,936	763,545	356,771
Bibliography		269,233	269,233	446,337
Management	20,524	(53)	20,471	67,935
Librarianship	<u>85,631</u>	<u>239,466</u>	<u>325,097</u>	<u>535,583</u>
Total program	134,106	1,870,890	2,004,996	1,692,216
Administration	<u>214,393</u>	<u> </u>	<u>214,393</u>	<u>185,810</u>
Total expenses	<u>348,499</u>	<u>\$1,870,890</u>	<u>2,219,389</u>	<u>1,878,026</u>
Excess of revenues over expenses	384,271		384,271	356,201
Fund balance, begin- ning of year	<u>1,859,820</u>	<u> </u>	<u>1,859,820</u>	<u>1,503,619</u>
Fund balance, end of year	<u>\$2,244,091</u>	<u> </u>	<u>\$2,244,091</u>	<u>\$1,859,820</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

STATEMENT OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1986

(With Comparative Totals for 1985)

	Library Operations				Librarianship	Total Program	Administration	Year ended June 30	
	Research	Resources	Bibliography	Management				1986	1985
Unrestricted									
Grants and contracts		\$ 33,420			\$ 76,000	\$ 109,420		\$ 109,420	\$ 95,913
Refunds and overappropriations		(19,011)			(881)	(19,892)		(19,892)	(8,116)
Staff and travel	\$ 101			\$16,653	312	17,066	\$109,072	126,138	163,946
Advisory committees					10,026	10,026		10,026	39
Consultants	566	200				766	18,322	19,088	24,444
Office expenses	12,675				174	12,849	16,423	29,272	29,083
Support services				3,871		3,871	70,576	74,447	143,876
	<u>13,342</u>	<u>14,609</u>		<u>20,524</u>	<u>85,631</u>	<u>134,106</u>	<u>214,393</u>	<u>348,499</u>	<u>449,185</u>
Restricted									
Grants and contracts	403,000	540,378	\$ 91,535		149,655	1,184,568		1,184,568	822,332
Refunds and overappropriations		(4,357)	(687)	(53)	(1,137)	(6,234)		(6,234)	(124,750)
Staff and travel	84,789	84,656	57,589		38,209	265,243		265,243	166,876
Advisory committees	15,506	29,727	18,032		1,450	64,715		64,715	131,227
Consultants	34,891	8,819	47,931		800	92,441		92,441	181,133
Office expenses		6,619	4,977		633	12,229		12,229	36,125
Support services	75,122	83,094	49,856		49,856	257,928		257,928	215,898
	<u>613,308</u>	<u>748,936</u>	<u>269,233</u>	<u>(53)</u>	<u>239,466</u>	<u>1,870,890</u>		<u>1,870,890</u>	<u>1,428,841</u>
Total expenses	<u>\$626,650</u>	<u>\$763,545</u>	<u>\$269,233</u>	<u>\$20,471</u>	<u>\$325,097</u>	<u>\$2,004,996</u>	<u>\$214,393</u>	<u>\$2,219,389</u>	<u>\$1,878,026</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Statements of Changes in Cash and Short-term Investments

	<u>Year ended June 30</u>	
	<u>1986</u>	<u>1985</u>
Sources of cash and short-term investments		
Excess of revenues over expenses	\$ 384,271	\$ 356,201
Increase in grants and contracts payable	544,991	
Increase in deferred income		764,363
Decrease in grants receivable	<u>2,454,836</u>	
	<u>3,384,098</u>	<u>1,120,564</u>
Uses of cash and short-term investments		
Increase in grants receivable		832,800
Decrease in deferred income	2,496,890	
Decrease in grants and contracts payable		328,503
Other	<u>4,604</u>	<u>12,174</u>
	<u>2,501,494</u>	<u>1,173,477</u>
Increase (decrease) in cash and short-term investments for the year	882,604	(52,913)
Cash and short-term investments, beginning of year	<u>3,479,759</u>	<u>3,532,672</u>
Cash and short-term investments, end of year	<u>\$4,362,363</u>	<u>\$3,479,759</u>

Notes to Financial Statements

JUNE 30, 1986 AND 1985

Note 1—Organization

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research. The Council's operations are financed through unrestricted general support grants and through several restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work through directly administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

The Council is an exempt operating foundation. Accordingly, it is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3). Under the provisions of the Tax Reform Act of 1984, the Council is no longer subject to the 2% excise tax on investment income commencing with fiscal year 1986.

Note 2—Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

The Council's financial statements have been prepared on the accrual basis of accounting. The significant accounting policies followed in the preparation of the financial statements are described below.

Grants

Grants are recorded as receivables and deferred revenue when the Council is notified that it has been awarded the funds. Unrestricted grant revenue is recognized in accordance with the budgeted annual payments specified by the grantors. Restricted grant revenue is recognized when the related expenses are incurred.

Grant and contract expenses are recorded when the recipients are notified that they are to receive the funds. Current period expenses are reduced for grant refunds and overappropriations.

Investments and investment income

Short-term investments, which primarily consist of treasury bills and interests in a money market fund, are recorded at cost which approximates market. Investment income is not restricted by the related grants and accordingly is recognized as unrestricted revenue.

Functional allocation of expenses

Costs of providing the various programs of the Council have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Certain indirect costs identified as support services costs have been allocated to programs and administration on a systematic basis. These costs primarily include salary, benefits, rent and other expenses.

Furniture and equipment

The costs of office furniture and equipment are consistently charged to expense when incurred. The Council does not consider such expenditures to be sufficiently material to warrant capitalization and depreciation.

Note 3—Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's defined contribution retirement annuity program administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the plan provide for full and immediate vesting of both the Council's and employees' contributions. The Council's contribution was \$55,000 and \$51,000 for fiscal years 1986 and 1985, respectively.

Note 4—Commitments

The Council entered into a lease agreement for office space expiring in 1987. The minimum future rental commitment as of June 30, 1986 is approximately \$127,000 for fiscal year 1987.

In September 1982, the Council entered into an agreement to sublease a portion of its leased office space. The rent income from the sublease amounted to approximately \$30,000 in fiscal year 1986 and was used to offset office rent expense.

Note 5—Pending Grant Transfer

On July 1, 1986 the Council was notified by a grantor foundation that it intends to redesignate a grant, presently awarded to the Council, when and if the present subrecipient receives its Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3) status ruling. The Council plans to reduce the related grant receivable and deferred revenue related to this restricted grant (\$496,000 at June 30, 1986) when it is notified that the designation of the grant has been changed.

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